

Peatlands in Focus at the 14th European Conference on Ecological Restoration

The 2024 European Conference on Ecological Restoration was held on 26-30 August in the city of Tartu, Estonia with 674 participants from 47 countries attending on site and even more online. The conference was co-organised by the Society for Ecological Restoration Europe Chapter, University of Tartu, and the Estonian Seminatural Community

Conservation Association (Pärandkoosluste Kaitse Ühing).

The theme of the Congress was "Bridging Science, Practice and Policy of Nature Restoration", which was very timely a week after the Nature Restoration Law in the EU came into effect on Sunday 18 August as noted by one of the plenary

Pathways to Peatland Forest Restoration were presented at the conference by peatland experts from Estonia and Finland: Triin Tekko (University of Tartu), Liisa Ukonmaanaho (Natural Resources Institute Finland Luke, Session Chair), Helena Rautakoski (Finnish Meteorological Institute), Liisa Maanavilja, Maija Lampela, Oona Allonen (all three from the Geological Survey of Finland), Nina Kumpulainen (University of Eastern Finland) and Tuula Larmola (Luke, Session Chair).

Visit to Laiuse restored peat extraction area. Dr Ain Kull (first from the right) demonstrated the greenhouse gas and biodiversity studies at the experimental area on the former peat extraction site. Photo: Tuula Larmola

speakers Dr Florian Claeys from the European Commission Directorate General for Environment.

He will be one of those responsible for the Nature Restoration Law and its implementation, including development of national restoration plans and the establishment of monitoring and reporting arrangements.

The event attracted land and water managers, conservation officers, scientists, representatives of non-governmental organisations and those of companies, and students involved in the restoration of a wide range of habitats and species from all around the world.

The conference consisted of sessions specific to ecosystems: including forest, peatland, wetland, grassland, dryland, cities, mining quarries, rivers, the Baltic Sea, marine, as well as cross-cutting themes on rewilding, nature conservation, and the technical, legal and financing aspects of restoration. Two poster sessions on these topics and several workshops and crash courses on stakeholder engagement, remote sensing, and nature-based solutions were organised.

Citizen science at Tudusoo mire. Succession in the mire lagg area after the restoration of the hydrological regime in 2021 is being monitored by photos taken by visitors on this fixed spot. Photo: Tuula Larmola

Twenty-five excursions also facilitated networking. A panel discussion with panellists from funding organisations, the banking sector, and a start-up provided further perspectives on climate and biodiversity finance strategies, practices, and business approaches.

The Society for Ecological Restoration also released its recommendations on effective implementation of the EU Nature Restoration Law on 30 August (please see more on their webpage <https://chapter.ser.org/europe/2024/09/04/tartu-declaration-of-sere2024-make-it-happen>).

Altogether, the participants heard over 400 presentations over four days.

Peatland Restoration

Peatlands and wetlands were on the agenda every day. Selected highlights included a plenary talk by Marko Kohv (University of Tartu) about the land use history, current state and prospects of Estonia mires, and a special session jointly organised by the four EU-funded projects (ALFAwetlands, RESTORE4CS, REWET, WETHORIZON) on wetland restoration and its trade-offs and co-benefits to climate, biodiversity and ecosystem services.

This was followed by a session on remote sensing of peatland ecology and restoration. The peatland sessions were concluded on the last conference day by the session "Pathways to peatland forest restoration", in which different management options and their climate and biodiversity impacts were discussed by several peatland experts, many of whom are also members of the IPS (photos on previous pages).

Several of the 25 excursions allowed the participants to experience Estonian peatlands.

I had the opportunity to participate in a full-day field trip to three restored peatlands in Northern and Eastern Estonia: Paraspõllu spring-fed fen, Tudusoo raised bog and Laiuse former peat extraction area, guided by Jüri-Ott Salm, Piret Pungas-Kohv (both Estonian Fund for Nature), Raimo Pajula (University of Tallinn), and Ain Kull (University of Tartu). The trip featured restoration methods and their success at the sites, as well

experiencing the bog with all senses, including a quick swim in a bog lake.

Networking, Cultural and Social Events

The venue, the Estonian National Museum, also invited the participants to familiarise themselves with the history of the Estonian people and that of their Finno-Ugric language relatives in a very informative and engaging manner.

The evenings were spent at an icebreaking party, welcome reception, both by the Emajõgi River, on further tours to explore Estonian nature and culture, as well as a conference dinner at the AHHA Science Centre, combining excellent food, fun and educational science activities, music, and dance.

All in all, the organisers led by Professor Aveliina Helm and Professor Triin Reitalu (both University of Tartu, Landscape Biodiversity Working Group) succeeded in creating an unforgettable conference experience. For more information on the event, visit www.sere2024.org.

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Expanding bog hollow at Tudusoo mire after damming ditches in the ombrotrophic bog part. Photo: Tuula Larmola